

A New Generation of Liquid Lasers from Engineered Perovskite Nanocrystals with Giant Optical Gain

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ABSTRACT:

With the development of optofluidic technology, liquid lasers have attracted intense interest but still face a formidable challenge due to the lack of qualified gain media and creative device design. Compared to the organic fluorescent dyes and traditional CdSe-based nanocrystals (NCs), the lead-halide perovskite (LHP) NCs feature larger gain coefficient and higher robustness, which renders LHP NCs a promising unexploited liquid gain medium. Herein, we for the first time demystify the hidden principle governing the solution-based light amplification in LHP NCs and demonstrate that the LHP NCs are superior solution-phase gain media showing a giant ($\sim 2600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) optical gain. On this basis, we design and realize a novel microfluidic laser device that exhibits a record-low pump threshold ($\sim 22.7 \text{ } \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$), high Q-factor (~ 7480), large output polarization (~ 0.91) and long-time robustness over high-intensity operation, which is readily applicable to practical applications. The findings represent a significant step toward the technologically important liquid lasers of new generation and could advance the optofluidic applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

Solution-based coherent light sources or liquid lasers are attracting more and more attention driven by the booming development of optofluidic technology, where optics and liquids are adopted synergistically to bring about novel functionalities.^[1-4] Compared to solid-state lasers consisted of close-packed gain materials, liquid lasers exhibit unique characteristics, enabling the generation of highly compact and integrated devices upon the marriage of microfluidics and photonics, which hold great promise for applications of flexible optoelectronics, label-free chemical detection, biomedical diagnosis and wearable devices.^[4-11]

The solution-phase gain medium represents the key element of a liquid laser and its iteration is critical to the development of optofluidic technology. Initially, the proposal of fluorescent dyes as liquid gain media has been widely investigated.^[5-6, 8, 12-13] In these dye liquid lasers, the complicated pumping and operation configurations are required to overcome the irreversible conversion of the dye gain medium to non-fluorescent molecules at stationary state.^[14] Even so, the dye molecules gradually photodegrade during optical excitation, resulting in diminished gain efficiency and necessitating periodic solution replacements.^[12] In recent years, a few reports have examined the possibility of CdSe-based quantum dots for liquid laser by virtue of the much improved robustness against external perturbations compared to organic dyes.^[4, 7, 9-11] However, due to the relatively low gain coefficient, the pump thresholds of these devices are too high (nearly hundreds of $\mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$) to be applicable for practical applications. Therefore, it would be highly desirable to seek new gain candidates for

developing high-performance liquid lasers.

Recently, the inorganic lead halide perovskite (LHP) nanocrystals (NCs) are emerging as the new class of lasing materials.^[15-17] Compared to the traditional CdSe-based NCs,^[18-21] the LHP NCs feature the large gain coefficient and high defect tolerance,^[15-17, 22-23] which renders LHP NCs a potentially qualified liquid gain medium. However, despite that significant progress has been made in developing LHP NC-based solid lasers in the past few years, the expansion of the success to liquid lasers from LHP NCs remain far lagged.^[15-16, 24-26] This could be attributed to the different mechanisms that dictate the optical gain or lasing performance for LHP NCs in solution compared to that in solid counterparts. Given the merits of LHP NCs for gain applications, it is imperative to figure out the hidden principle governing the LHP NC-based light amplification in solution and, on basis of this, develop the novel enabling liquid lasers.

In this work, we for the first time demonstrate that the LHP NCs are intrinsically superior liquid gain media exhibiting a giant ($\sim 2600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) optical gain by comprehensive transient absorption (TA) and contrast spectroscopic experiments. We clarify that the relatively poor colloidal dispersibility and pump-induced deactivation of the NCs are the main mechanisms blocking the optical amplification from liquid LHP NCs. With the above issues solved simultaneously by rationally designed alkyl sulfonate anchoring, the low-threshold light amplification from solution-phase CsPbBr₃ NCs is achieved. On this basis, we design and realize the microfluidic laser device that integrates the fluidic channel, optical fiber and CsPbBr₃ NC solution. By

virtue of the excellent gain property of the LHP NCs and the benign optical feedback provided by the microchannel device, the microfluidic laser exhibits a record-low pump threshold ($\sim 22.7 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$), extremely high Q-factor (~ 7480), large polarization (~ 0.91) and long-time robustness over high-intensity operation. Such liquid laser device could be readily applicable to practical applications thanks to distinguished stability and low threshold that is affordable by the commercially available cheap pump sources. These results provide a protocol for realizing a next generation of liquid lasers and offer new possibilities for micro-optofluidic fields.

2. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

To test the possibility of liquid optical amplification from LHP NCs, the classic oleic acid and oleylamine capped (OA/OAm)-CsPbBr₃ NCs are excited in solution by the striping pumping configuration (see details in the Supporting Information), as schematized in the Figure 1a. We can see that only the broadband spontaneous emission spectra can be observed with the increase of pump fluence until the output intensity stops growing (Figure 1b), indicating the absence of light amplification. It is known that the colloidal concentration is an important parameter for solution-phase gain media.^[4, 7, 10-11, 27] Therefore, we varied the concentration of OA/OAm-CsPbBr₃ NCs for further attempt. However, we found that the colloidal dispersibility of OA/OAm-CsPbBr₃ NCs is relatively poor. As revealed by the in-situ absorption measurement, the OA/OAm-CsPbBr₃ NC can only be well dispersed up to 80 mg mL⁻¹ (Figure S1a), which is much lower than those of the CdSe-based QDs.^[28] Unsurprisingly, the light amplification fails to occur across the available

concentrations.

Furthermore, in comparison with the spontaneous emission, the light amplification in gain media typically requires more intense optical excitation. In this regard, what happens for the NCs under such harsh condition would be important and may determine the optical gain performance of CsPbBr₃ NCs in liquid phase. To figure out this issue, the femtosecond TA measurements are performed under varied excitation intensities (see details in the Supporting Information). The average carrier number $\langle N_0 \rangle$ per CsPbBr₃ NC was calculated based on the Poisson distribution (Figure S2). The typical pseudo-color TA spectra and corresponding spectral distributions at various delay times are plotted in Figures 1c and 1d for OA/OAm-CsPbBr₃ NCs ($\langle N_0 \rangle \sim 0.5$), where a prominent photo-bleaching (PB) signal is observed at ~ 500 nm due to state filling effect and charge-induced Stark effect.^[29-30] The decay curves of the PB signal under varied excitation densities are tracked in Figure 1e. It is seen that the decay rate of OA/OAm-CsPbBr₃ NCs increases with the rising of excitation fluence, which is attributed to the occurrence of multiexcitonic Auger recombination. However, with the further increase of pump intensity, the decay was discovered to persistently increase under high photoexcited carrier densities without any sign of saturation, which is different from the behavior of Auger recombination and indicates the generation of carrier traps that increase the decay rate under high pump intensities.^[31] According to literature,^[32-34] the OA/OAm ligands feature a highly dynamic binding state due to the reversible protonated and deprotonated processes, therefore, the ligands tend to escape from the surface of NCs

under harsh external perturbation, such as the intense optical excitation applied here. The detachment of the ligands would activate severe carrier traps and induce irreversible damage on the sample. To further confirm the hypothesis, we investigate the change in the carrier dynamics before and after the high-intensity excitation ($\langle N_0 \rangle > 10$ for 30 minutes) as shown in Figure 1f. It turns out that after intense photoexcitation, the PB kinetics of OA/OAm-NCs irreversibly deviates from its original trend, which shows an accelerated recombination rate, thus confirming the permanent damage of the NCs. Moreover, the escape of ligands makes these particles unstable and prone to aggregation, resulting in the further loss of emission activity, which is manifested by the distinct decrease of the amplitude of PB signal compared to that under the same excitation intensity before laser irradiation (the inset of Figure 1f).

Based on the above finding, we can conclude that the poor colloidal dispersibility and/or the pump-induced deactivation of the NCs are likely the main limiting factors blocking the optical amplification from liquid LHP NCs. Bearing this in mind, we propose that a highly dispersible and optically robust LHP NCs with strong ligand binding might be required to achieve solution-phase optical amplification and lasing. In this sense, alkyl sulfonate anchoring on CsPbBr₃ NCs (e.g., dodecylbenzene sulfonic acid (DSA)) might be a promising solution in terms of the following aspects: First, the DSA ligands with long chain of multi-carbons exhibit strong steric repulsion that would enable favorable colloidal dispersibility.^[32-33, 35-36] Second, the sulfonate heads in DSA ligands can link tightly with the Pb ions to form a

steady bonding state because the binding energy between sulfonate group and Pb ions is much higher than that between OAm and Pb ions.^[32, 34, 36] The DSA-CsPbBr₃ NCs are fabricated by a modified hot-injection method (see details in the Supporting Information).^[32, 34, 36] The size of the DSA-CsPbBr₃ NCs is similar to that of the OA/OAm-CsPbBr₃ NCs (~8 nm), and the comparable size of the two NCs is also manifested by the similar absorption and emission spectra (Figure S1d). Indeed, it is found that the DSA-CsPbBr₃ NCs show much improved colloidal dispersibility in solution than that of OA/OAm ones. Specifically, the DSA-CsPbBr₃ NCs can be well dispersed up to ~180.0 mg mL⁻¹ without indication of any particle interaction or aggregation, which is demonstrated by the linear increase of the absorption coefficient with concentration (Figure S1b and S1c). Figure 2a shows the excitation fluence dependent PL spectra from DSA-CsPbBr₃ NC solution using the same stripe pumping configuration as above. We can see that the broad PL spectra are initially observed at low pump intensities, then, a narrow peak with full width at half-maximum (FWHM) of 3.2 nm at ~525 nm appears when the pump intensities reach 12.6 μJ cm⁻². This new emission peak gradually dominates the PL spectrum as the pumping intensity increases, indicating the development of optical amplification or stimulated emission (SE) in DSA-NC solution. The plot of the integrated emission intensity as a function of the pump fluence is presented in Figure 2b, which reconfirms the buildup of light amplification with an extremely low threshold (~11.7 μJ cm⁻²) in solution. Consistently, a distinctly bright spot for DSA-NCs (inset of Figure 2a) is observed on the side of the quartz cuvette. Furthermore, the influence of the NC concentration on

the solution-based optical amplification is evaluated (Figure S3). It is found that the lowest concentration required for the appearance of SE is $\sim 133.0 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$, which is much higher than the viable concentration of OA/OAm-CsPbBr₃ NCs. With the increase of the NC concentration, the SE threshold gradually decreases owing to the elevation of the effective gain medium and the threshold reaches the lowest ($11.7 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$) at a concentration of $\sim 177.9 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$. As the concentration further increases beyond the optimal dispersibility, the NCs tend to clustering and partially lose their emissive activity, accompanied by scattering and intraparticle energy transfer losses. Concentration-dependent saturation of PL intensity caused by concentration quenching has also been observed in colloidal solution.^[37] These behaviors lead to the observed increase in the threshold until the SE phenomenon disappears at a concentration value of $\sim 282.0 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$.

The TA spectroscopy is also performed on the DSA-CsPbBr₃ NC solution to gain more insight. Figures 2c and 2d exhibit the pseudo-color TA spectra and corresponding profiles as functions of wavelength and delay time ($\langle N_0 \rangle \sim 0.5$) with a strong PB signal at a wavelength of $\sim 500 \text{ nm}$. The carrier kinetics of the DSA-NCs under high excitation densities are interrogated in Figure 2e. With the further increase of pump intensity, the decay of DSA-NCs stays nearly unchanged when the pump fluence reaches a certain value, which is in stark contrast to the persistently increased decay for the OA/OAm-NCs. More importantly, there is nearly no detectable change in the decay dynamics and the amplitude of PB signal for DSA-NCs before and after high-intensity excitation, indicating the robustness of the DSA-NCs against intense

photoexcitation (Figure 2f). These observations illustrate that DSA-NCs does not expose damage caused by ligand shedding during the intense pumping, which is consistent with the high binding energy between sulfonate group and Pb ions. The material optical gain g_i by TA technique is generally defined as $g_i = -A$ ($A = \Delta A + A_0$), where A_0 is the static absorbance prior to excitation and ΔA is the absorbance change after excitation. We further map out the color-coded regions of the net gain spectrum under a high excitation density of $\langle N_0 \rangle \sim 10$ for the DSA-NCs (Figure 3a) with the gain coefficients g_i calculated in the figure (see details on calculation in the Supporting Information). The gain bandwidth is determined to be ~ 120 meV, and net optical gain can persist up to ~ 100 ps. A more detailed analysis of the gain is presented in Figure 3b, recorded for material gain spectra under carrier densities near and above the gain threshold. The gain spectra are red-shifted relative to the steady-state absorbance spectrum and show a continuously increased gain coefficient with increasing carrier density. The material gain coefficient of the DSA-NCs appears to keep growing until 2600 cm^{-1} for the highest carrier density ($\langle N_0 \rangle \sim 21$) afforded by our setup (Figure 3c), and does not display a trend towards saturation. Such nearly unsaturated optical gain in intact DSA-NCs is consisted with the intrinsically superior gain property of halide perovskite semiconductors.^[15] To further explore the gain behavior at high carrier density, we monitor the fluence dependence of the buildup and decay of optical gain in Figure 3d. The delayed formation of the gain at high carrier density is derived from the slow carrier relaxation by the apparent cooling bottleneck in halide perovskites.^[38] More importantly, gain lifetime accompanied by

the increase of gain coefficient is accordingly prolonged, consistent with the unchanged decay kinetics at high densities (Figure 2e). In contrast, the OA/OAm-NCs show severe drops in the maximum gain value and gain lifetime with increasing the carrier density (Figure S4), which coincides with the dramatic detachment of ligands and the subsequent activation of carrier trapping and degradation under intense photoexcitation (Figure 1e). As a result, the remarkable optical gain characteristics of DSA-NCs allow it to achieve light amplification in solution eventually.

In view of the superior gain performance of solution-based DSA-CsPbBr₃ NCs, a microfluidic device providing optical feedback is designed to develop liquid lasing. The fluidic channel is made by the process shown in Figure 4a. Briefly, a 40 mm long and 10 mm wide U-shaped fluidic channel with a cross-section of $250 \times 250 \mu\text{m}^2$ was incised by a micro-control system. The prepared chip and bonding substrate were then ultrasonically cleaned in deionized water at 50 °C for 3 times and dried in a vacuum oven at 80 °C for 30 minutes. Then, a segment of optical fiber with 80 μm radius and 30 mm length was inserted in the micro-channel, which is adopted to provide evanescent wave pumped whispering gallery mode (WGM) feedback (Figure 4c). Following this, the device was encapsulated by N₂O plasma bonding and two pinheads were switched in the fluidic channels as ports for the inflow and outflow of the NC solution (the photograph of the fabricated microfluidic device is shown in Figure 4b, see the details of fabrication process in the Supporting Information). Here, hexane is selected as the solvent since it shows a lower refractive index (~ 1.37) than that of silica fiber (~ 1.46) to satisfy total internal reflection required for WGM lasing.

In this configuration, the WGM inside the microcavity extends to the gain medium of the NC solution by evanescent field so as to provide the optical feedback. Figure 4c and the inset of Figure 5a show the schematic and photograph of the operating liquid laser, the excitation beam is focused into a circle spot to irradiate the liquid gain medium around the fiber. Figure 5a shows the pump fluence dependent lasing spectra from the microfluidic device. With increasing the excitation intensity, a successive evolution from a broad spontaneous emission spectrum to the sharp emission peaks is observed. The nonlinear dependence of integrated PL intensity on pump intensities is shown in the Figure S5a, which indicates the lasing action with a record-low threshold of $\sim 22.7 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ among all of the NC liquid lasers.^[4, 7, 9-11] Such low pump threshold can be well affordable by the commercially available cheap lasers, such as the fiber lasers. The lasing mechanism is demonstrated as WGM by calculating the lasing modes and the free spectral range (FSR) (Figure 5b).^[39] For a fiber of radius (R) = 80 μm , the lasing wavelength well matches the constant mode spacing of $\sim 0.36 \text{ nm}$ and the corresponding azimuthal mode are numbered from 1443 to 1458. To understand the resonance of the cylindrical microcavity, the electric field distribution in the transverse cross-section of the optical fiber is numerically simulated with the refractive index of the fiber is $n_1 = 1.46$, and the refractive index of the surrounding gain medium is $n_2 = 1.37$. A TE polarized (consistent with the emission polarization measured later) electric field intensity distribution with a radial mode number $r = 1$ is shown in the inset of Figure 5b, and it can be seen that the optical modes are well confined within the transverse cross-section of the optical fiber. Given that only the

NCs near the surface of the fiber are excited by the evanescent wave, the higher-order radial modes would not be activated. Hence, we only consider the case of $r = 1$, which coincides well with the high Q-factor measured experimentally (Figure S5b). The microchannel waveguide configuration utilized in our work enhances the light-matter reaction and reduces the lasing threshold. The fiber used here provides the necessary total internal reflection condition for the construction of a WGM microlaser with high Q-factor, otherwise only the amplified spontaneous emission can be achieved. The corresponding Q-factor (~ 7480 , calculated by: $Q = \lambda/\delta\lambda$, where λ and $\delta\lambda$ is the center wavelength of lasing peak and the FWHM of the lasing peak, respectively) is much higher than those of the previously reported solid-state NC lasers,^[24, 40-41] which can be ascribed to the suppressed losses in our case with respect to that of the film lasers such as the optical scattering. The normalized radial intensity distribution of the cylindrical microcavity is shown in Figure S5c. One can see that the extension of evanescent-field terminates near the outside of the cavity boundary, indicating that the gain comes from excited NCs in the region of near field. We further investigate the emission polarization of the laser device. Figure S5d illustrates the integrated PL intensity as a function of linear polarizer angle at a fixed excitation intensity (see experimental details in the Supporting Information). The well-fitted integrated intensity by Malus' law specifies that the polarization is transverse electric (TE) mode. The degree of polarization (P) is calculated to be as high as 0.91 by $P = (I_{\perp} - I_{\parallel})/(I_{\perp} + I_{\parallel})$, where I_{\perp} and I_{\parallel} represent the lasing intensities perpendicular and parallel to the fiber axis, respectively. Thanks to the facile microchannel configuration,

the lasing mode can be tuned by replacing the fibers with different diameters in the fluidic pipeline. The lasing results from varied fibers are shown in Figure 5c and the mode numbers are marked accordingly. According to the WGM theory, the FSR is inversely proportional to the size of a cavity. As R is decreased from 44 μm to 12 μm , the FSR increases from 0.67 nm to 2.44 nm, and the corresponding number of angular modes is reduced from 12 to 2.

By virtue of the fluidic nature and isolation from the external environment of the liquid gain medium, the distinguished stability, as another important factor for practical applications, of microfluidic laser operation is anticipated. A set of control experiments is implemented to test the robustness of our device. Three silica fibers of the same size were adopted as resonators for solution-based DSA-NCs, film-based DSA-NCs and film-based OA/OAm-NCs, respectively (see the fabrication of NC film-based laser in Supporting Information), with uninterrupted excitation for over ~ 4 hours (corresponding to $\sim 1.4 \times 10^7$ laser shots) at room temperature and the same high excitation fluence of $\sim 173.1 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$. As shown in Figure 5d, for the liquid DSA-NCs laser, no distinct decrease of lasing intensity is observed during the entire measurement. However, the lasing intensity from the film-based DSA-NCs drops sharply at ~ 30 minutes, and then gradually descends to $\sim 56\%$ of its initial intensity. In the case of OA/OAm-NC film, the lasing signal cannot be detected after 1.5 hours where a continuous decline has been experienced. In addition, it is revealed that the lasing peak position of solution-based DSA-NCs laser does not shift with increasing pump fluence (Figure 5a), while the change of lasing wavelength is often observed

from solid-state NC films, which was ascribed to irreversible thermal effects, photo-induced size changes of NCs or the dielectric effect.^[39, 42] The combined merits of our liquid laser including low threshold, high Q-factor, large output polarization and high stability render it readily applicable for practical applications and indicate its bright future as the powerful coherent light sources in liquid photonics.

3. CONCLUSION

In summary, we developed a new type of low-threshold and robust liquid lasers based on perovskite NCs with giant optical gain. We clarified the underlying mechanisms blocking the liquid lasing in perovskite NCs and solved the issues simultaneously by alkyl sulfonate anchoring. Based on this, the high-performance microfluidic lasers are realized by the evanescent coupling from the excited NCs outside the microcavity. In the future, thanks to the facile emission color tunability of perovskite NCs by halide exchange, we can anticipate the extension of the microfluidic laser to multiple channel laser arrays and the different micro-fluidic channels can be filled with halide-tuned perovskite NCs to achieve on-demand lasing colors for on-chip fluidic coherent light sources.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

Data Availability Statement

Research data are not shared.

Keywords

liquid laser, microfluidics, perovskite nanocrystals, optical gain, transient absorption

Figure 1. (a) The design for excitation of solution-based nanocrystals (NCs). (b) Photoluminescence (PL) spectra of OA/OAm-CsPbBr₃ NC solution in a quartz cuvette at various pump intensities. Inset shows the photograph of the cuvette contained with OA/OAm-NC solution. (c) Pseudocolor transient absorption (TA) spectroscopies of OA/OAm-NCs at $\langle N_0 \rangle \sim 0.5$, and (d) corresponding spectral distribution at different delay times. (e) Normalized pump fluence-dependent TA kinetics extracted from the photobleaching (PB) regions of OA/OAm-NCs. (f) Comparison of carrier dynamic at $\langle N_0 \rangle < 0.3$ before and after high power density laser beam shining ($\langle N_0 \rangle > 20$) for OA/OAm-NCs. Inset: Comparison of the intensity of original PB signal amplitude.

Figure 2. (a) PL spectra of DSA-CsPbBr₃ NC solution in a quartz cuvette at various pump intensities. Inset shows the photograph of the cuvette contained with DSA-NC solution. (b) The emission intensity of DSA-NCs as a function of the pump intensity. (c) Pseudocolor TA spectroscopies of DSA-NCs at $\langle N_0 \rangle \sim 0.5$, and (d) corresponding spectral distribution at different delay times. (e) Normalized pump fluence-dependent TA kinetics extracted from the PB regions of DSA-NCs. (f) Comparison of carrier dynamic at $\langle N_0 \rangle < 0.3$ before and after high power density laser beam shining ($\langle N_0 \rangle > 20$) for DSA-NCs. Inset: Comparison of the intensity of original PB signal amplitude.

Figure 3. (a) Net gain maps of DSA-CsPbBr₃ NCs at $\langle N_0 \rangle \sim 10.4$. (b) Material gain spectra g_i (cm^{-1}) and linear absorption (dotted line) of DSA-NCs for different carrier densities showing a transition from net absorption to net gain. (c) The maximum gain coefficient as a function of carrier density for DSA-NCs. (d) The fluence dependent kinetics of the buildup and decay of optical gain for DSA-NCs, probed at 525 nm where the non-linear absorbance turns negative ($A < 0$) and net optical gain g_i occurs ($g_i > 0$).

Figure 4. (a) Fabrication process of the microfluidic device. (b) Photograph of a blank microfluidic device. (c) Illustration of a fiber microfluidic laser and the whispering gallery mode (WGM) resonance mechanism.

Figure 5. (a) Lasing spectra of the microfluidic laser at various pump intensities. Inset: Photograph of a microfluidic laser under excitation. (b) The mode analysis of one WGM lasing spectrum with the azimuthal mode numbers from 1443 to 1458. Inset: The distribution of electric field intensity in the transverse cross-section of a cylindrical cavity. (c) WGM modulation from fibers of different radii in DSA-NC solution. (d) The normalized peak intensity of solution-based lasing and film-based lasing under the constant excitation with a high intensity = $173.1 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$

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The table of contents entry:

We demystify the hidden principle governing the solution-based light amplification in perovskite nanocrystals and demonstrate that the perovskite nanocrystals are superior solution-phase gain media showing a giant optical gain by rationally designed alkyl sulfonate anchoring. On this basis, we realize a microfluidic laser device that exhibits a low pump threshold, high Q-factor and long-time robustness over high-intensity operation.

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A New Generation of Liquid Lasers from Engineered Perovskite Nanocrystals with Giant Optical Gain

Table of Content Graphic:

